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A chlorine based detector ($\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$) for 2.5 MeV neutron spectroscopy in deuterium nuclear fusion plasmas with enhanced particle discrimination algorithm

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Abstract

Neutron emission spectroscopy is an effective nuclear fusion plasma diagnostics technique for diagnosing the fuel ion populations on fusion plasma experiments. The state of the art 2.5 MeV neutron spectrometer for deuterium plasmas is based on the time of flight (TOF) technique, which however requires the development of large scale instruments. No compact alternatives that approach the performance of TOF have been found so far. Liquid and plastic scintillators have limited spectroscopic capabilities due to their non-peaked response to monoenergetic neutrons. In the last years, Chlorine based scintillators have been explored. In these instruments, neutron detection is based on the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)^{35}\text{S}$ nuclear reaction, which results in a Gaussian peak in the recorded neutron energy spectrum. In this context, one option is offered by CLYC scintillators, which have the drawback of a limited counting rate capability (a few tens of kHz). Another option is offered by the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillators, which combine a comparable energy resolution and, most importantly, a faster signal ($<1 \mu\text{s}$) enabling measurements at higher counting rates. On the other hand, LaCl_3 has a more challenging particle discrimination. The standard method based on pulse shape analysis provides a limited particle identification and poses restrictions in the counting rate capability of the instruments. An innovative particle

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identification algorithm based on Fourier Transforms has been developed providing higher accuracy and effectiveness. In this paper, we present the performance of a 2.5 MeV neutron spectrometer based on a LaCl_3 scintillator in terms of pulse shape discrimination and energy resolution. Results are used to discuss their use for neutron spectroscopy applications in tokamak plasmas.

Keywords: plasma diagnostics, neutron spectroscopy, neutron emission spectroscopy, nuclear fusion plasma diagnostics, LaCl_3 scintillator

1. Introduction

Neutron emission spectroscopy along a collimated line of sight is an effective nuclear fusion plasma technique for diagnosing fusion plasma experiments. In particular, in deuterium plasmas, neutrons with an energy distribution centered around 2.45 MeV are directly emitted by nuclear fusion reactions carrying information on the fuel ions population. The width and the energy position of the neutron peak provide information on the ion temperature and plasma rotation velocity. Furthermore, the investigation on high energy tails, which are typically of low intensities, allows investigating the effectiveness of the external heating systems and the diagnosis of fast ions [1–3]. The state of the art neutron spectrometer for deuterium plasmas is based on the time of flight (TOF) technique, like the ones installed at the joint European torus (JET) [4] and at the experimental advanced superconducting tokamak (EAST) [5]. However, they require the development of relatively bulky instruments which can be difficult to integrate with the existing machines where space availability is limited and, furthermore, they cannot be installed on a multi-line-of-sight camera [6]. No compact alternatives that approach the performance of TOF have been found so far. Liquid and plastic scintillators have intrinsically limited spectroscopic capabilities due to their principle of operation. Here neutron detection exploits the neutron scattering reactions on hydrogen resulting in a flat energy spectrum to mono-energetic neutrons [7]. In the last years, Chlorine based scintillators have been explored to fill the gap between TOF spectrometers and organic scintillators. In these instruments, neutron detection is mainly based on the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)^{35}\text{S}$ nuclear reaction, which results in a Gaussian peak in the recorded neutron energy spectrum for monoenergetic neutrons in the range 1–5 MeV. The peak is caused by the full energy deposition of the produced proton inside the crystal which has the energy of the incoming neutron plus the Q -value of the reaction which is 0.615 MeV. The amount of generated scintillation light is quenched by a factor depending on the origin of the particle that excites the molecules making up the crystal. This results in a peak at a certain electron equivalent energy position [8, 9]. Other weaker $n\text{-}^{35}\text{Cl}$ reaction channels are available (see figure 1) such as the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)^{35}\text{S}^*$ leaving the $^{35}\text{S}^*$ in the excited states and the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha)^{32}\text{P}$ leaving the ^{32}P nuclei in ground state or in the excited state, with Q -value = 938keV and Q -value = 860keV for the ground state and the first excited state, respectively. The reaction channels, together with their Q -value are summarized in table 1.

So far, the most used chlorine based scintillator is the $\text{Cs}_2\text{LiYCl}_6\text{:Ce}$ (C^7LYC) crystal enriched with ^7Li , which has been exploited both at EAST [11] and at ASDEX Upgrade [12]. The CLYC has superior particle identification capability but its use as a compact neutron spectrometer is however limited to a few tens of kHz counting rates due to its slow scintillation time (\sim a few μs). Another option is offered by the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillators, which combine a comparable energy resolution and, most importantly, a faster signal (<200 ns) enabling measurements at higher counting rates, which is important in nuclear fusion experiments. On the other hand, $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ has a more challenging particle discrimination which varies accordingly on the Ce-doped concentration [13]. In this work, an innovative algorithm for particle discrimination based on Fourier Transform has been developed providing higher accuracy and effectiveness. The paper is organized as follows: a description of the detector and the first measurements of its intrinsic activity are presented in section 2, together with the particle discrimination based on the standard pulse shape technique. The 2.5 MeV neutron characterization measurements performed at the low-scatter measurement hall of the Physikalisch–Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) in Germany are presented in section 3 while section 4 is dedicated to the new development of a particle identification algorithm based on Fourier transform. Section 5 is dedicated to 2.5 MeV neutron measurements performed at the neutron irradiation laboratory for electronics (NILE) facility at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in UK. Here the detector has been exposed to a mix neutron/gamma flux with significant gamma background and neutron scattered component to mock up the harsh environment of a fusion experiment. A discussion on the role of a 2.5 MeV neutron spectrometer based on a $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator in future fusion experiments is given in section 6, together with the conclusions. In this paper the measured energy spectra are given in MeVee (MeV electron equivalent).

2. Detector description and pulse shape discrimination

The 2.5 MeV neutron spectrometer here proposed for fusion plasma application is based on a $1' \times 1'$ cylindrical $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator crystal with standard Ce-doped concentration manufactured by Saint-Gobain Crystals (now Luxium Solutions [14]). The scintillation crystal has a light yield of 49

Figure 1. Cross sections of the different reaction channels from ENDF/B-VIII.0 library [10].

Table 1. Reaction channels between the ^{35}Cl and the neutrons, together with their Q -value [8].

Reaction	Channel	Q -value- E^* [keV]
$^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)^{35}\text{S}$	g.s.	615
	1st e.s.	-956
	2nd e.s.	-1376
$^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha)^{32}\text{P}$	g.s.	938
	1st e.s.	860
	2nd e.s.	425.1

photons/keV and a fast scintillation decay time component of 28 ns. A slower scintillation decay component is also present with weak intensity. The crystal is coupled to an Hamamatsu [15] photomultiplier tube (PMT) model R9420-100-10. Due to its hygroscopicity, the crystal is encapsulated into a sealed aluminum case provided with a glass window on one end, allowing the scintillation light to get out and hit the photocathode of the PMT. Photoelectrons are then generated and multiplied by the series of dynodes inside the PMT, converting the light signal into an electrical signal. Then the output signal is directly fed into a digitizer that, for all the experiments described in this paper, is a CAEN [16] digitizer DT5730 with 500 MS^{-1} sampling rate and 14-bits resolution. The digitizer allows to sample each waveform and to store them for a post processing analysis. First characterization measurements with gamma ray sources have been done at the CNR-ISTP laboratories in Milano in order to calibrate the detector, to evaluate its energy resolution and the length of the output signal. Standard laboratory sources with 37 kBq nominal activity have been used exploiting ^{137}Cs , ^{60}Co and ^{22}Na radioactive isotopes, emitting the following gamma ray lines:

- 0.662 MeV from ^{137}Cs .
- 1.173 MeV and 1.332 MeV from ^{60}Co .
- 0.511 and 1.275 MeV from ^{22}Na .

Figure 2. Recorded energy spectrum due to internal activity of the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator (bottom) and the related 2D scatterplot of the PSD values (top). The purple rectangles highlight the alpha events due to the presence of ^{227}Ac isotopes and daughters inside the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillation crystal. The description of the experimental setup is provided in the main text.

The detector energy resolution calculated as the ratio between the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the full energy peak and the energy of the peak resulted to be about 4% at 0.662 MeV which decreases as $1/\sqrt{E_\gamma}$ for higher energies. The presence inside the crystal of the unstable ^{138}La isotope and the presence of the ^{227}Ac and its daughters as impurity, offer the possibility to study the pulse shape discrimination capability of the detector. ^{138}La , in fact, decays by electron capture with consequent emission of a gamma ray at about 1436 keV and an x-ray of a few tens of keV, or by β^- decay which, in addition, produce a continuum contribution above 0.8 MeV. The region between 1.5 MeV and 2.5 MeV is characterized by the alpha decays of the ^{227}Ac and daughters (see figure 2-bottom). The particle identification based on pulse shape discrimination is performed integrating the waveforms over a short gate and a long gate and computing the PSD value for each event as $PSD = (Q_{\text{long}} - Q_{\text{short}})/Q_{\text{long}}$, where Q_{long} and the Q_{short} represent the integral over the long and the short gates, respectively. The length of the two gates has been optimized in order to enhance the pulse shape discrimination based on the figure-of-merit (FOM)

Figure 3. PSD spectrum obtained as the y -projection of the 2D scatterplot of the PSD values. The PSD spectrum is related to the measurement of the internal activity of the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator shown in figure 2.

$$FOM = \frac{d}{FWHM_\gamma - FWHM_\alpha}$$

of the PSD spectrum (see figure 3) which is the projection of the 2D scatterplot of the PSD values (see figure 2-top). $FWHM_\gamma$ is the FWHM of the PSD spectrum related to gamma events, $FWHM_\alpha$ is the FWHM of the PSD spectrum related to alpha events, while d is the distance between the two peaks of the PSD spectrum. In this case, the FOM is calculated taking into accounts the events with energy higher than 1.2 MeVee. The maximum FOM obtained is 1.24 ± 0.01 with a long gate of 660ns and a short gate of 100 ns.

3. 2.5 MeV neutron measurements at the PTB

The 2.5 MeV neutron characterization measurements of the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator have been performed at the PTB in open geometry in the low-scatter measurement hall of the PTB accelerator facility (PIAF) [17]. Neutrons were produced by accelerating a deuterium beam into an 850 hPa gas target made by D_2 molecules, exploiting the ${}^2\text{H}(d,n){}^3\text{He}$ nuclear fusion reactions. 2.5 MeV neutrons were selected by placing the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ detector at 105° with respect to the incoming ion beam at a distance of 150 cm from the target (see figure 4). The detector has been calibrated *in-situ* with gamma ray sources of ${}^{137}\text{Cs}$, ${}^{22}\text{Na}$ and ${}^{88}\text{Y}$. The latter emits two gamma-ray lines at 0.898 MeV and 1.836 MeV, allowing a calibration that covers a wide energy range. During the neutron experiment, every recorded waveform was stored allowing a post processing analysis in order to investigate the particle discrimination of the detector. Based on the optimal long gate and short gate values, the 2D scatterplot of the PSD values has been produced (see figure 5-top) allowing to identify the different contributions to the energy spectrum (see figure 6). Different PSD values refer to different particles that slow down inside the crystal

Figure 4. A picture of the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ detector installed in the low-scatter measurement hall of the PTB accelerator facility. The spectrometer is visible on the left lying on two red supports. On the right side of the picture, the deuterated target together with part of the beam-line are shown.

and deposit their energy. A gamma-ray contribution, always present when dealing with neutrons, can be identified in the region centered at PSD around 0.21, while the α contribution due to intrinsic activity of the crystal stands at PSD values around 0.25. The 2.5 MeV neutron events exploiting the ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p){}^{35}\text{S}$ nuclear reaction results in a clear blob centered at 0.23 and are highlighted in the graph with a red circle. These events result in a clear peak in the recorded energy spectrum. It is centered at 2.2MeVee which translates in a quenching factor of about 0.7 for protons. The PSD regions related to gamma, proton and alpha events have been used to select and separate the contribution of the different particles in the recorded energy spectrum and to elaborate the average waveform for each particle (see figure 7). The small differences in the shape of the three waveforms make the pulse shape discrimination of $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator challenging. The FOMs calculated when an energy threshold = 1.7 MeVee is applied, resulted to be: $FOM_{\gamma\alpha} = 1.51 \pm 0.03$, $FOM_{\gamma p} = 0.57 \pm 0.01$ and $FOM_{p\alpha} = 0.9 \pm 0.2$. The limited pulse shape discrimination capability can also be qualitatively observed by looking at the 2D scatterplot of the PSD values and the PSD distribution (see figure 8). The gamma contribution, in fact, partially overlap to the proton events. However, the energy spectra generated by different particles can be extracted as shown in 6.

4. Particle discrimination based on Fourier Transform

Due to the intrinsic limitations of the standard particle discrimination method based on the pulse shape analysis, an innovative algorithm based on Fourier transform has been designed for the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ crystal. A Python routine [18] which exploits the fast Fourier transform algorithm (FFT) to calculate the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) has been developed to improve the particle identification. The idea is to use the DFT to express the waveforms as the sum of periodic components in the frequency domain. The DFT $y[k]$ of length

Figure 5. 2D scatterplot of the PSD values calculated for the 2.5 MeV neutron spectroscopy measurement at PTB (top) and the associated recorded energy spectrum (bottom). The purple rectangle represent the alpha events due to intrinsic activity of the crystal, events in the red circle are due to $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, \alpha)$ nuclear reactions, while events in the purple rectangle in the region 0.8–1 MeV are due to $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, \alpha)$ and $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p)$ nuclear reactions. Due to limited statistics p and α cannot be distinguished.

N of the waveform $x[n]$ is defined as following [19]:

$$y[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N} n} x[n].$$

The digitized waveforms are discrete sequences of real values and the DFT separates its input into components that contribute at discrete frequencies [20]. The $y[k]$ are complex-values representing the amplitude and phase of the sinusoidal components that make up the signal $x[n]$. The magnitude indicates the amplitude of the frequency component k in the original signal and the set of magnitudes, referred as the amplitude spectrum, shows how the amplitudes are distributed between the frequencies from 0 to $f/2$, where f is the sampling frequency of the digitizer (500MHz). The amplitude spectrum provides information about how much each frequency contributes to the original signal. Example of the amplitude spectrum calculated for the gamma, proton and alpha particles recorded with the $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ crystal are shown in figure 9. An innovative algorithm based on the integration of the DFT amplitude spectrum over two gates has been developed. Their ratio provides

Figure 6. Total energy spectra measured at PTB with 2.5 MeV neutrons and the different components due to different particles.

Figure 7. Averaged waveforms recorded from gamma, alpha and proton events. The waveforms are normalized to 1.

a quantitative value, here called amplitude Fourier shape discrimination (AFSD), which is the analogous to the PSD value of the standard pulse shape discrimination method. The formula used to compute the AFSD is:

$$AFSD = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^j \|y[k_n]\|}{\sum_{n=0}^i \|y[k_n]\|}$$

where (i, j) are the indices which define the integration range of the short gate and the long gate. The AFSD parameter allows to bring out the differences between waveforms, highlighting the frequencies that contributes more. The optimal short gate resulted to be from 0MHz to 10MHz, while the long gate from 0MHz to the maximum frequency analyzed (250MHz). The choice of the gates have been based on the optimization of the FOMs. The best FOMs are: $FOM_{\gamma\alpha} = 2.18 \pm 0.02$, $FOM_{\gamma p} = 1.14 \pm 0.01$ and $FOM_{p\alpha} = 1.09 \pm 0.01$ and they have been calculated from the AFSD spectrum

Figure 8. PSD spectrum obtained as the projection of the 2D scatterplot of the PSD values shown in figure 2 with threshold equal to 1.7 MeV.

Figure 9. Amplitude spectrum of the averaged waveforms of gamma, alpha and proton.

shown in figure 10, which is the y-projection of the 2D scatterplot of the AFSD values in figure 11. A sensitivity study of the FOM has also been performed as a function of the length of the waveform considered for the FFT from 100ns up to 1000 ns. Excellent results have been obtained even at 100 ns with almost no degradation of the particle discrimination capability of the instrument with respect to 1000ns. The improvement brought by the new algorithm has allowed for a better identification of the protons. In particular, the (n,p) peak can be clearly recognized in the scatterplot (red circle) and it is completely separated from the gamma contribution. A low-energy tail in the 1.2MeVee—1.8MeVee region, resulting from the scattered neutron component undergoing (n,p) reactions, can also be observed. In addition, a small peak in the region 0.7MeVee—1.2MeVee due to reaction $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)^{35}\text{S}^*$ leaving the $^{35}\text{S}^*$ in the 1st excited state can be identified. The ratio between the intensity of the peak due to the ground state

Figure 10. AFSD spectrum obtained as the projection of the 2D scatterplot of the AFSD values with threshold equal to 1.7MeVee.

Figure 11. 2D scatterplot of the AFSD obtained with 2.5MeV neutron measurement analyzed with the FFT algorithm. Events within the two red curves are related to protons. The red circle identifies the (n, p) peak. Alpha components are highlighted in purple.

channel of the (n,p) reaction and the one related to the first excited state is ~ 20 , which is perfectly in agreement with the value found by Kuvin *et al* in [21]. The (n,α) peak due to $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha)^{32}\text{P}$ reaction can also be observed in the energy region 0.6 MeVee—1 MeVee. The recorded energy spectra related to the (n,p) and (n,α) reactions are shown in details in figure 12.

5. 2.5 MeV neutron measurements at NILE

The NILE at the RAL (in UK) is a new facility equipped with compact deuterium–deuterium and deuterium–tritium neutron generators for mono-energetic 2.5MeV and 14MeV neutrons, respectively [22]. Due to the presence of significant amount of gamma background and thermal and scattered neutrons,

Figure 12. Energy spectra due to (n), (p) and (n,α) reactions. The alpha contribution due to the intrinsic activity of the LaCl_3 crystal is not shown.

the radiation field of NILE is significantly more complex than metrology laboratories, such as PTB [23]. This allows to test the detector performances in a more realistic environment similar to the one of a fusion experiments. The $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ detector has been previously calibrated with ^{137}Cs , ^{22}Na and ^{88}Y and then placed at 90° with respect to the deuterium beam impinging on the deuterium target. The enhanced particle identification algorithm based on FFT was able to discriminate the challenging radiation field and to isolate the direct 2.5MeV neutron peak. Figure shows a comparison between the 2D scatterplot obtained with the standard PSD method and the enhanced FFT method. While with the standard PSD method the 2.5MeV neutron peak overlaps with the gamma background, in the FFT method they result completely separated (see figure 13).

6. Discussion and conclusions

Characterization measurements of a $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ scintillator with 2.5MeV neutrons and gamma rays has been performed to investigate its performances for DD fusion plasma applications. Its pulse shape discrimination capability based on the charge integration of the waveforms has been demonstrated. However, it resulted to be less effective with respect to the $\text{FOM}_{\gamma p}$ found in [24] and [13], indicating a higher Ce-doped concentration. In particular, this can also be observed from the comparison between the waveforms achieved in this work and the ones showed in [13, 24]. In the present article the difference in the γ and proton waveforms is mainly in the first 80 ns (the fast component of the scintillation light). In contrast, in Kormilitsyn *et al* and Vuong *et al* articles the differences in the γ and proton waveforms mainly lie in the slow component of the scintillation light. In the present article, the biggest improvement has been done by developing a new algorithm based on FFT that makes the commercially available $\text{LaCl}_3(\text{Ce})$ crystals suitable for neutron spectroscopy. The

Figure 13. Comparison of the 2D scatterplot obtained with the standard PSD method (top) and the FFT method (bottom) using the measurements at NILE.

Table 2. Summary of the obtained FOMs with the two particle identification methods.

Method	$\text{FOM}_{\gamma\alpha}$	$\text{FOM}_{\gamma p}$	$\text{FOM}_{p\alpha}$
PSD	1.51 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.01	0.9 ± 0.2
FFT	2.18 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.01

FOMs achieved with the FFT method are significantly higher than the ones obtained with the standard PSD method, as shown in table 2.

In addition, FFT can be efficiently calculated on field programmable gate array allowing for measuring fast neutrons with real time particle discrimination capability. Standard pulse shape discrimination of the LaCl_3 relies on the charge integration of the waveform over a long gate (600ns), taking into account the slow scintillation component which is of weak intensity and only appreciable in logarithmic scale. While pile-up events occurring in the slow component of the signals do not significantly affect the measured energy spectra, the requirement for a long gate to enable particle discrimination limits the detector's maximum count rate. The FFT has proven to be effective in processing the fast component of the signal without degrading the particle discrimination capability and there is no benefit in considering the slow scintillation component. This opens up to high counting rate measurements

(500kcps) which are needed to cope with the high neutron and γ fluxes expected at ASDEX Upgrade [12]. For this reason, an upgrade of the 2.5MeV neutron spectrometer installed at ASDEX Upgrade will be performed by replacing the CLYC scintillator with a LaCl_3 crystal. The energy resolution of the LaCl_3 detector resulted to be about 10% for 2.5MeV neutrons and its main contribution ($\sim 8\%$) is due to the kinematic of the (n,p) reaction inside the crystal [24]. The developed detector successfully fulfill the requirements for neutron spectroscopy on DD fusion plasma, by matching count rate capability, n/ γ discrimination and energy resolution. Its compactness make the instrument suitable for installation on existing machines in which the available space could be limited. Furthermore, they can be installed on multi-line-of-sight cameras combining spectroscopy and tomography.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researcher. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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